

D7.3 OPTIPATH Plan for Dissemination and Communication

Grant agreement no.:
101185769

Project acronym:
OPTIPATH

Project full title:
Adaptive optical metasurfaces for real-time, label-free and non-destructive 7D digital pathology

HORIZON EIC Grants

HORIZON-EIC-2024-PATHFINDEROPEN-01-01

Start date of project: 2025-02-01
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D7.3

Plan for Dissemination and Communication Activities

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Organization name of lead contractor for this deliverable:
SINTEF AS

Project funded by the European Union		
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	x
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
CI	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.	

Deliverable number:	D7.3
Deliverable name:	Plan for Dissemination and Communication
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Abstract
This report presents the OPTIPATH Plan for Dissemination and Communication Activities.

Public introduction
This report describes the plans for dissemination and communication in the EIC Pathfinder Open project – OPTIPATH. It builds on Sec. 2.3 Dissemination and Communication in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement (ID 101185769), aiming to elaborate and concretize the various activities.

Introduction

Below a planning canvas is used to elaborate and concretize the goals for Dissemination and Communication presented in Sec. 2.3 in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement (ID 101185769). This is performed for three phases of the project: “Project start”, “R&D/Piloting phase”, and “Project end”. For each targeted activity goals, channels, timing/frequency, target groups, responsibility and KPIs are defined.

Dissemination and communication plan

PROJECT START – Main objective: Presentation of the project

ACTION	GOAL	CHANNELS	YEAR/FREQUENCY	TARGET GROUP	RESPONSIBLE	EFFECT
What?	Why?	Where?	When?	Who?	Who?	KPI
Webpage for the project	To have information about the project and contact information available to everyone who wants to learn more and contact us.	EU-webpage	Y1 Project start	Society at large, industry and public sector, scientific community, partners in academia, decision makers, clients	Project manager / all partners	Number of visitors
Scientific contributions to conferences and trade events	Establish research and industrial relations and potential future partnerships.	Laser World of Photonics, SPIE Strasbourg, Metamaterials Congress, NIL industrial day, EPIC events, ATTRACT conference, national conferences	Identify 1-2 events per semester	Research and industrial communities within biosensing, medical diagnostics and photonics.	SINTEF will lead the work and assign responsibilities to the partners	Attendance, list of connections made.
Press release to the media	To effectively reach out to all the relevant media channels at once.	NTB (Norwegian news agency)	Y1 Project start / 1	Society at large, industry and public sector, decision makers, politicians	SINTEF will lead the work and assign responsibilities to the partners	Number of media outlets that pick up the story
Share news in social media channels	To draw attention to the project by posting interesting content and news.	Make OPTIPATH LinkedIn page	Y1 Project start	Society at large, scientific community, partners in academia, clients, decision makers	Project manager / all partners	Number of followers
Visual identity (e.g. logo, presentation template)	A strong visual identity is important for recognizability.	To use in different channels to promote the project (e.g. website, presentations, social media channels)	Y1 Project start	All receivers of material produced by the project.	Project manager	Feedback from selected receivers on visual appearance.

R&D/PILOTING PHASE – Main objective: Presentation of activities and results

ACTION	GOAL	CHANNELS	YEAR/FREQUENCY	TARGET GROUP	RESPONSIBLE	EFFECT
What?	Why?	Where?	When?	Who?	Who?	KPI
Scientific contributions to conferences and trade events	Establish research and industrial relations and potential future partnerships.	Laser World of Photonics, SPIE Strasbourg, Metamaterials Congress, NIL industrial day, EPIC events, ATTRACT	Each partner should identify 1-2 events per semester	Research communities within biosensing, diagnostics and photonics.	All partners	Attendance, list of connections made.

		conference, IEEE Photonics Europe, Advanced Optical Imaging Technologies, national conferences				
Scientific publications in high impact Journals	Share generated knowledge with research community and gain visibility for research activity	Will target high impact and open access journals, adhering to Open Science principles.	Each partner should target 1-2 papers per year.	Research communities within biosensing, diagnostics and photonics.	All partners should be involved, but particularly the university partners should lead the manuscript preparation work.	>5 publications in high quality open access journals such as Nature Communications, Optica, ACS Nano, Optics Express, Biomedical Optics Express, Journal of Biomedical optics.
Newsletters, Webinars and educational videos	Highlight relevance of OPTIPATH towards current histopathological assessment and needs within optics industry	Share via project website and social media, and promote through participation in trade events.	We aim for 4 items per year.	Medical research community and practitioners, industrial stakeholders, authorities and public figures.	The work will be led by SINTEF which will assign responsibilities to all partners	Visibility metrics in Social Media and number of views of the videos made.
High impact events	Ensure uptake of the developed technology and secure funding for further development	Industrial conferences and tech summits such as ATTRACT Final conference in Brussels, EU research and innovation days.	1-2 events per year per partner	Medical research community and practitioners, industrial stakeholders, authorities and public figures.	The work will be led by SINTEF which will assign responsibilities to all partners	We aim to attend more than 6 high impact events.
News article on each partner's website and tips to the media about the article	To spread news about the project to different target groups. To get publicity about the project in different channels. To show the impact the project has on society.	Each partners website. Media: Relevant newspapers (e.g. afterposten.no), research websites (e.g. forskning.no)	Upon every publication we should explore the possibility of making a related news article / press release.	Scientific community, partners in academia, industry and business, clients, decision makers	Project manager / all partners	Antall saker / Antall medier som plukker opp saken
Blog posts	To reach out to the scientific community / those who are interested in the technology	The SINTEF blog	Upon every publication we should explore the possibility of making a related blog post.	Scientific community, partners in academia	Project manager	Number of readers
Share news in social media channels	To draw attention to the project by posting interesting content and news.	LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram	Y3 Project end	Society at large, scientific community, partners in academia, clients, decision makers	Project manager / all partners	Number of followers
Share results with COST TETRA initiative (European Cooperation in Science & Technology)	COST TETRA (The mETamaterial foRmalism approach to recognize cAncer) establishes a relevant network of researchers.	Attend workshops arranged by COST TETRA and attempt to become part of the national management committees	1-2 events per year	European research network within use of metamaterials for cancer diagnostics	University of Aston	Number of events attended and number of spin-out initiatives created.

PROJECT END – Main objective: Presentation of the project

ACTION	GOAL	CHANNELS	YEAR/FREQUENCY	TARGET GROUP	RESPONSIBLE	EFFECT
What?	Why?	Where?	When?	Who?	Who?	KPI
<i>Scientific papers in high impact Journal</i>	<i>Share generated knowledge with research community and gain visibility for research activity</i>	<i>Will target high impact and open access journals, adhering to Open Science principles.</i>	<i>Each partner should target 1-2 papers per year.</i>	<i>Research communities within biosensing, diagnostics and photonics.</i>	<i>All partners should be involved, but particularly the university partners should lead the manuscript preparation work.</i>	<i>>5 publications throughout the duration of the project in high quality open access journals such as Nature Communications, Optica, ACS Nano, Optics Express, Biomedical Optics Express, Journal of Biomedical optics.</i>
<i>Arrange and attend Industrial and Scientific Workshops</i>	<i>Showcase developed technologies to ensure market up-take</i>	<i>We can aim to arrange such workshops in affiliation with relevant exhibitions, such as Laser World of Photonics in Munich in 2027.</i>	<i>1-2 events towards the end of the project.</i>	<i>Industrial and research community with medical diagnostics and optics.</i>	<i>NILT leads the exploitation task, but will involve all partners.</i>	<i>Connections made for further research and innovation activities.</i>
<i>Press release to the media</i>	<i>To effectively reach out to all the relevant media channels at once.</i>	<i>NTB (Norwegian news agency)</i>	<i>Y3 Project end</i>	<i>Society at large, industry and public sector, decision makers, politicians</i>	<i>SINTEF will lead the work and assign responsibilities to the partners</i>	<i>Number of media outlets that pick up the story</i>
<i>Reporting</i>	<i>To increase visibility for the project.</i>	<i>E.g. public deliverables.</i>	<i>Y3 Project end</i>	<i>Society at large, industry and public sector, decision makers, politicians</i>	<i>Project manager</i>	